

Empirical Evaluation of Web Based Personal Name Disambiguation Techniques

Dr.A.Suruliandi¹ and Selvaperumal.P²

¹Professor, Department of Computer science and Engineering,
ManonmaniamSundaranarUniversity, Tirunelveli, India

²Research scholar, Department of Computer science and Engineering,
ManonmaniamSundaranar University, Tirunelveli, India

Abstract

Personal name ambiguity in the web arises when different people share the same name in the web. Resolving the name ambiguity in the web is useful in a number of applications like Information retrieval, Information extraction and Question and answering system etc. A general name disambiguation process involves clustering the web pages such that each cluster represents an ambiguous person. In this article, five important name disambiguation techniques that make use of Hierarchical agglomerative clustering are empirically compared. Experiments were conducted on the benchmark dataset and their performances are evaluated in terms of purity, Inverse purity and f-score. Results show the method that uses features like Lexical, linguistic and personal information hierarchical agglomerative clustering performs better than disambiguation using other techniques.

Keywords

Personal name disambiguation, Entity name resolution, web page clustering.

1.Introduction

In the web, entities names are highly ambiguous. There are two types of ambiguities as far as entity names are concerned. A single entity having multiple names and multiple entities sharing a single name. Solving the former problem is known as alias extraction [1], and the latter is known as personal name disambiguation. Name ambiguity refers to the problem of two or more entities sharing the same name. This is in contrast to alias names, where several name refers to the same entity. Name disambiguation involves correctly predicting the number of persons sharing the ambiguous name and clustering the web pages such that each person's document needs to be in a single cluster.

Name disambiguation is a special case of entity name disambiguation. Sub fields of entity disambiguation includes name disambiguation, place name disambiguation [2], organizational name disambiguation [3] etc. In general personal name disambiguation arises when two or more persons are referred by the same name. Name ambiguity arises when the same name refers to multiple entities. Retrieving all the entities that the name refers to decreases the precision of an Information retrieval system. Similarly In sentimental analysis the presence of ambiguous name decreases the accuracy of the system. In Question and answering system, the presence of name ambiguity makes it difficult to retrieve relevant answers to the questions from the web. Similarly in data integration, the presence of ambiguity challenges the integrity of the data.

People search engines like '411.com', 'PeopleFinder', 'people.yahoo.com' are increasingly becoming popular because of offering a capability to identifying an individual over the vast web space. People search, [4] involves name disambiguation is an inherent step. Name disambiguation has been a challenging problem in many application areas like Information retrieval, Social network extraction, Ontology integration, Information extraction, Question and answering system etc. Disambiguating a name will in turn improve the efficiency the aforementioned systems. A closely related area is social network extraction in which an inherent step is personal name disambiguation. In social network extraction, [5] name disambiguation is an integral part. A large number of social networking sites are offering people search facility to enable users to identify a specific individual who is sharing the name with several other persons. Name ambiguity also arises in the biomedical text documents. The ambiguity arises because of genes and proteins sharing the same name [6].

Most of the existing method uses bag of words model and named entities for web based name disambiguation. Methods employed may be local, which involves using words, named entities and keywords as features [7][8]. Some methods employ global features like usage of knowledge base and external corpora for the purpose [9]. Since there is no certainty that the all the words are unique to web pages of a particular individual, it is difficult to use just words as discriminative features. One alternative of this is limiting the scope of the words taken for consideration [10]. Named entities are considered to be the efficient feature for name disambiguation task as it can uniquely identify as person. The important step in all of the name disambiguation process is finding the discriminative features for the individual sharing the ambiguous name. Features extracted can be direct features and indirect features. Direct features extraction includes extracting n-grams, named entities, hyperlinks from the web pages of relevant persons and indirect features includes extracting features from the external knowledge bases.

Web People search workshops (WePS) is an evaluation campaign focuses on personal name disambiguation task. First WePS was conducted on 2007 followed by second on 2009 and third on 2010. WePS workshops involves two tracks namely clustering documents to solve the personal name ambiguity and extracting various information like dob, designation, Birthplace, occupation, phone etc for each person sharing the ambiguous name. Most of the systems in WePS uses named entities as main feature for name disambiguation tasks.

1.1. Relative work

Most of the previous works related to name disambiguation involves unsupervised clustering [11] [12] [13]. Ron Bekkerman, et al [14] used link structure and in another method they used Agglomerative/conglomerative double clustering for name disambiguation process. Their focus is on disambiguating name in social network and is quite different from disambiguating peoples' name in the web. Masaki et al, [8] proposed a two stage personal name disambiguation technique involving hard clustering and soft clustering. The extracted features like Nouns, Compound keywords and Urls from the data and first applied Hierarchical agglomerative clustering to cluster documents of same person. Compound keywords were then extracted from each of these clusters and are used as features for second stage soft clustering. There have been attempts to disambiguate names using knowledge of Wikipedia [15]. They used knowledge from Wikipedia to disambiguate names. They mapped ambiguous names to Wikipedia entry, making it difficult to apply for all the people names because of small coverage of personal names by Wikipedia. Other commonly used methods include usage of biographic features like name, occupation, location etc for disambiguation process. The problem with using biographic information from name disambiguation is, it is often impossible to extract the required biographic information for each person from the web. If a person is less visible in the web then it is not possible to extract all the biographic information required for disambiguation process. Zhengzhong Liu et al, [16] proposed a clustering algorithm for name disambiguation using topic information.

Their method extracts web page title, URL, meta data, words in the web page etc as feature vector followed by merging of clusters sharing similar topics. Yiming Lu et al, [17] used web corpora to increase the accuracy of author name disambiguation system. They considered if two papers appear in the same page, both of it belong to the same author. Using web connection as well as a series of constraints they disambiguated author names. V.Kalashnikov [18]exploits a variety of semantic information like named entities, hyperlinks etc to construct a Entity-Relationship graph to disambiguate names in web pages. They proposed a method for web people search that makes use of name disambiguation to facilitate better people search. kazunari Sugiyama et al,[19] used Semi supervised approach for name disambiguation in the web. He uses seed pages to guide the clustering process. Zhao Lu et al, [20]proposed ontology based name disambiguation model. They first constructed an ontology with large set of instances followed by creation of temporary instance and extraction of features from the web. The similarity between temporary instance and the instance in the ontology to find the appropriate personal name. Xianpei Han et al, [21] used reference entity tables mined from the web for name disambiguation. They used web querying to construct reference table then personal names are disambiguated by linking them to the entries in the reference table. The exhaustive literature survey conducted shows that resolving name disambiguation problem is far from over because of the following challenges.

1. The number of persons sharing the ambiguous names keeps increasing as the time go by.
2. Challenge of finding the number of persons sharing the ambiguous name (Which is required before performing the clustering).
3. The unstructured nature of the web content and difficulty in extracting features for clustering.
4. The cost and resource required to construct knowledge base if external resources are used for resolving name ambiguity.

1.2.Motivation and Justification

Personal name queries accounts for 5% of search queries in search engine[22].Over the years, a range of techniques like usage of ontologies, reference table and extraction of different features etc have been proposed for web based name disambiguation problem. To the best of authors' knowledge, there are not many papersevaluating the performance of existing name disambiguation techniques. Motivated by this, in this paper five significant work of name disambiguation is empirically evaluated using benchmark dataset.

Hierarchical agglomerative clustering is the commonly used clustering algorithms for name disambiguation process. Most of the method uses internal features like tokens, nouns, and biographic features etc as discriminative features for disambiguation process. Justified by this, in this paper five important works of name disambiguation process is empirically evaluated.

2.Method

2.1.Term-Entity based name disambiguation

Term-entities are set of terms or named entities that uniquely represents a person. Bollegala et al,[7] proposed an unsupervised method based on term-entity model for automatically disambiguating people name. They used nouns, nouns phrases and keywords extracting from the web for the process. They represented each person sharing the ambiguous name in term-entity model and used group average agglomerative clustering to cluster documents that belong to the same person. Fig 1 shows various steps involved in the process.

Fig 1: Term-Entity based name disambiguation process

The name disambiguation method involves the following steps.

Step 1: query the search engine with “personal name” and get top ‘n’ web pages.

Step 2: Extract terms and named entities in the web pages using POS tagger that contains the ambiguous personal name.

Step 3: Group average agglomerative clustering is performed to assign each document in a cluster (i.e hard clustering). Terminate the clustering process when the clustering quality reaches a predefined value.

Care is taken such that the number of clusters formed is equal to the number of persons sharing the ambiguous name in the web page collection. The method uses a predefined threshold value of cluster quality, which is the optimum number of clusters to be formed. The threshold is calculated with the help of experimental dataset.

Experiments have shown that the use of noun and noun phrases alone forms good feature for clustering process. Since the method relies mainly on nouns and terms, the method is simple and robust for name disambiguation process. Extracting a large number of terms is computationally expensive and using all these terms may not always yield better clustering results. The predefined value computed using experiment dataset will not always suitable for all the dataset.

$$\text{Disambiguation Accuracy} = \frac{\sum_i A(i, i)}{\sum_{i, j} A(i, j)}$$

Where, A(i,j) is the number of person i, predicted as j, and A(i,i) is the number of persons i correctly predicted as i.

2.2. Two stage clustering

Masaki Ikeda et al, [8] proposed two stage clustering name disambiguation process involving two stage clustering. The process involved is represented in fig 2. He found that extracting features from the whole document gives better results than fixing a limited window size for feature extraction.

Fig 2: Two stage clustering based name disambiguation process

The process involved is explained in the following procedure.

Step 1: In the web page collection, extract named entity features, compound keywords (compound nouns), link features(URL's)

Step2: Extracted features are then used for hierarchical agglomerative clustering (Hard clustering) and use group average method for finding distance between clusters.

Step 3: Extract compound keywords again from the resulting cluster,

Step4: Perform clustering process with the extracted compound keywords until required number of clusters are generated.

Since Entity names, compound keywords, urls are important features in name disambiguation process, this method exploits these potent features for the process. The use of two stage clustering hard followed by soft clustering provides robust results than simple hard clustering. Soft clustering approach does not always suits well for name disambiguation because in the web, most of the web pages belongs to a single person sharing the ambiguous name and a single web page containing names of multiple persons sharing the name.

2.3. Disambiguation with rich features

ErginElmacioglu et al, [10] method views name disambiguation clustering as hard clustering problem. It is based on extracting variety of features from the web and are input as vector of features to the hierarchical agglomerative clustering algorithm. Fig 3 shows the process involved in name disambiguation using rich set of features.

Fig 3: Name disambiguation using rich features set

The process involves the following steps

Step 1: Extract Tokens, Named entities, Hostnames and domains, Page URL's from the web page collection.

Step 2: Perform Hierarchical agglomerative clustering with the feature vectors

Step 3: Iterate the clustering process until desirable number of clusters are generated.

The use of features in the web pages like Tokens, Named entities produce robust results in clustering. The method is simple and easy to implement. Name disambiguation cannot always be successful using the features in the web pages alone. The use of external features and features from link structure can be better exploited for resolving name ambiguity.

2.4. Unsupervised name disambiguation

S. Mann et al, [23] used rich set of biographic information as features for clustering process. The method uses language independent bootstrapping process for extracting these features. It explores the use of different features ranging from simple words in the web pages to important and relevant words (tf-idf), biographical features and so on. Fig 4 shows the actual process involved in name disambiguation process with unsupervised learning.

Fig 4: Unsupervised name disambiguation

Procedure involved in the process is as follows

Step 1: Extract Nouns, basic biographic information (dob, occupation, designation etc), tf-idf(term-inverse document frequency) from the document collection.

Step 2: Perform Hierarchical agglomerative clustering with the feature vectors

Step 3: Terminate the clustering process when the desirable number of clusters are generated.

The use of nouns, biographic information works well for name disambiguation process. The use of external knowledge base like Wikipedia may increase the accuracy of the system.

2.5. Disambiguation using Lexical, linguistic and personal features

Xiaojun Wan et al, [13] proposed a method called Web hawk for name disambiguation that leverages on Lexical linguistic and personal information features for clustering. Lexical features includes title, words in the web pages, linguistic features includes Nouns, Noun phrases and personal information features includes person name, title, organization, email address and phone number. Fig 5 shows the process involved in disambiguation process. It involves the following process.

Step 1: Pre-process the document collection that includes removing web pages that refers to multiple persons sharing the ambiguous names, removing junk pages (pages referring to non-human names like ford, Bloomberg, Disney etc).

Step 2: Extract lexical, linguistic and personal information features from the document collection.

Step 3: Perform hierarchical agglomerative clustering and average-link method to compute the similarity between two clusters as follows

$$Sim(c1, c1) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n sim(p_i, p_j)}{m \times n}$$

Where p_i and p_j are the web pages and $c1, c2$ are clusters.

Fig 5: Disambiguation using lexical, linguistic and personal features

2.6. Hierarchical agglomerative clustering

HAC,[24] is a bottom up clustering method in which initially each document is treated as singleton cluster and successively similar pairs are merged (agglomerate) to form larger cluster until a single cluster containing all the documents is formed. It involves the following steps.

Step 1: Assign each document to individual cluster

Step 2: Construct distance matrix and look for the pair of matrix that are shortest from each other.

Step 3: Merge the clusters that are closest to each other.

Step 4: Find the distance between the new cluster with all the other clusters and update the distance matrix.

Step 5: Repeat the above steps until single cluster is formed or required number of clusters are formed.

Since the required number of clusters is not known a priori, when to terminate the clustering process is a significant factor in performance of clustering process. The use of different distance metrics for measuring distance between clusters may produce different results. Thus selection of distance parameter forms a vital part in clustering process. In the following experiments, group average agglomerative clustering is used to find the average distance between clusters. In group average clustering, the distance between two clusters is calculated average distance between data points in both the clusters. In practical, it is impossible to know what the 'n' value beforehand and different techniques have been devised to handle this problem [7].

3. Experimental results and Discussion

3.1. Dataset

In this experiment, two datasets are used. Danushka et al, [7] used names Jim Clark and Michael Jackson as dataset and in this paper, this dataset is referred as dataset I. In that dataset, the number of persons sharing the name and the number of contexts has been downsized for our convenience. In order to use benchmark dataset for the evaluation purpose, Pedersen and Kulkarni's data set is used. Pedersen and Kulkarni's data set, [25] contains data for five ambiguous names collected from the web. For these five names, they have collected the data, data formatted and cleaned. This dataset is hereafter referred as dataset – II. Table 1 and 2 shows the summary of dataset I and II.

Table 1: Summary of dataset – I.

Name	No. of persons sharing the name	Number of contexts
Jim Clark	6	230
Michael Jackson	2	90

Table 2: Summary of dataset – II.

Name	No. of persons sharing the name	Number of contexts
Richard Alston	2	247
Sarah Connor	2	150
George Miller	3	286
Ted Pedersen	4	333
Michael Collins	4	359

3.2 Performance metrics

The performance of clustering can be measured by Purity index, Inverse purity Index and harmonic mean of purity and inverse purity index, [26]. Purity index, [27] is the number of correctly assigned documents (majority) by number of documents.

$$Purity = \sum_I \frac{|C_i|}{N} \max_j \frac{|C_i \cap L_j|}{|C_i|}$$

Where C the set of clusters,L is the list of classes and N is the total number of documents clustered. Purity penalizes noise in the cluster.Inverse purity index, [28] rewards grouping items together.

$$InversePurity = \sum_I \frac{|L_i|}{N} \max_j \frac{|L_i \cap C_j|}{|L_i|}$$

F-score is the harmonic mean of purity and inverse purity value.

$$F - Score = \frac{2 * Purity * Inversepurity}{Purity + Inversepurity}$$

All of the above metrics ranges between 0 to 1, where 1 is the optimal value.

3.3.Results and Discussion

3.3.1 Experiments –I

The hierarchical agglomerative clustering is performed to produce ‘n’ number of clusters where ‘n’ is the number of persons sharing the ambiguous name. For the experiment, a part of web page in each of top 100 web pages returned by search engine is used. The performance of various methods for dataset-I can be seen in the table 3.

Table 3: Performance of various techniques on dataset - I.

Method	Purity Index	Inverse purity index	F-Score
Term-entity based model	0.69	0.83	0.75
Two stage clustering	0.65	0.78	0.70
Disambiguation with rich features	0.53	0.73	0.61
Unsupervised name disambiguation	0.63	0.81	0.70
using Lexical, linguistic and personal features	0.79	0.82	0.80

From the table 3 it is evident that the usage of lexical, linguistic and personal information discriminative features works well for name disambiguation task. Term-entity model that uses nouns and noun phrases as discriminative features also performs better in the disambiguation task.

3.3.2 Experiments – II

The same experiment is repeated with dataset – II using a portion of top 100 web pages returned by search engine for the name query. The performance of various methods for dataset-I can be seen in the table 4.

Table 4: Performance of various techniques on dataset - II.

Method	Purity Index	Inverse purity index	F-Score
Term-entity based model	0.73	0.81	0.76
Two stage clustering	0.59	0.71	0.64
Disambiguation with rich features	0.68	0.79	0.73
Unsupervised name disambiguation	0.71	0.73	0.71
using Lexical, linguistic and personal features	0.77	0.83	0.79

The performance of method that uses lexical, linguistic and personal info is evident from the table 4. This method outperforms the other methods both in terms of purity and inverse purity. Similar to experiment I, term entity based method performs well in the experiment II also. It can be inferred from the experiments that the usage of lexical, linguistic features along with nouns and noun phrases serves better for name discrimination tasks.

4. Conclusion

Considering the wider application of name disambiguation process, in this paper five important techniques of name disambiguation process is empirically evaluated. Experiment is conducted using benchmark dataset and the results are evaluated using standard metrics like purity, inverse purity and f-score values. Results show that method that uses features like Lexical, linguistic and personal information hierarchical agglomerative clustering performs better than other name disambiguation techniques taken for evaluation.

The work is prequel for proposing a novel web based name disambiguation technique. Disambiguating place names, product names etc are interesting topic to work on. The usage of name disambiguation process in a large number of applications like information retrieval, information extraction, document merging, question and answering etc are compelling areas to work on.

Reference

1. Bollegala, Danushka, Yutaka Matsuo, and Mitsuru Ishizuka. "Automatic discovery of personal name aliases from the web." *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* 23, no. 6 (2011): 831-844.
2. Overell, Simon, Joao Magalhaes, and Stefan Ruger. "Place disambiguation with co-occurrence models." In *CLEF 2006 Workshop, Working notes*. 2006.
3. Zhang, Shu, Jianwei Wu, Dequan Zheng, Yao Meng, and Hao Yu. "An adaptive method for organization name disambiguation with feature reinforcing." In *Proceedings of the 26th Pacific Asia Conference on Language, Information, and Computation*, pp. 237-245. 2012.
4. Kalashnikov, Dmitri V., Zhaoqi Chen, Sharad Mehrotra, and Rabia Nuray-Turan. "Web people search via connection analysis." *Knowledge and Data Engineering, IEEE Transactions on* 20, no. 11 (2008): 1550-1565.
5. Matsuo, Yutaka, Junichiro Mori, Masahiro Hamasaki, Takuichi Nishimura, Hideaki Takeda, Koiti Hasida, and Mitsuru Ishizuka. "POLYPHONET: an advanced social network extraction system

- from the web." *Web Semantics: Science, Services and Agents on the World Wide Web* 5, no. 4 (2007): 262-278.
6. Al-Mubaid, Hisham, and Ping Chen. "Biomedical term disambiguation: An application to gene-protein name disambiguation." In *Information Technology: New Generations*, 2006. ITNG 2006. Third International Conference on, pp. 606-612. IEEE, 2006.
 7. Bollegala, Danushka, Yutaka Matsuo, and Mitsuru Ishizuka. "Automatic annotation of ambiguous personal names on the web." *Computational Intelligence* 28, no. 3 (2012): 398-425.
 8. Ikeda, Masaki, Shingo Ono, Issei Sato, Minoru Yoshida, and Hiroshi Nakagawa. "Person name disambiguation on the web by two-stage clustering." In *2nd Web People Search Evaluation Workshop (WePS 2009)*, 18th WWW Conference. 2009.
 9. Nguyen, Hien T., and Tru H. Cao. "A knowledge-based approach to named entity disambiguation in news articles." In *AI 2007: Advances in Artificial Intelligence*, pp. 619-624. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2007.
 10. Elmacioglu, Ergin, Yee Fan Tan, Su Yan, Min-Yen Kan, and Dongwon Lee. "Psnus: Web people name disambiguation by simple clustering with rich features." In *Proceedings of the 4th International Workshop on Semantic Evaluations*, pp. 268-271. Association for Computational Linguistics, 2007.
 11. Chen, Ying, and James Martin. "Towards Robust Unsupervised Personal Name Disambiguation." In *EMNLP-CoNLL*, pp. 190-198. 2007.
 12. <http://www.d.umn.edu/~tpederse/namedata.html>
 13. Wan, Xiaojun, Jianfeng Gao, Mu Li, and Binggong Ding. "Person resolution in person search results: Webhawk." In *Proceedings of the 14th ACM international conference on Information and knowledge management*, pp. 163-170. ACM, 2005.
 14. Bekkerman, Ron, and Andrew McCallum. "Disambiguating web appearances of people in a social network." In *Proceedings of the 14th international conference on World Wide Web*, pp. 463-470. ACM, 2005.
 15. Bunescu, Razvan C., and Marius Pasca. "Using Encyclopedic Knowledge for Named entity Disambiguation." In *EACL*, vol. 6, pp. 9-16. 2006.
 16. Liu, Zhengzhong, Qin Lu, and Jian Xu. "High performance clustering for web person name disambiguation using topic capturing." *Ratio* (2011).
 17. Lu, Yiming, Zaiqing Nie, Taoyuan Cheng, Ying Gao, and Ji-Rong Wen. "Name disambiguation using Web connection." In *Proceedings of AAAI 2007 Workshop on Information Integration on the Web*. 2007.
 18. Bunescu, Razvan C., and Marius Pasca. "Using Encyclopedic Knowledge for Named entity Disambiguation." In *EACL*, vol. 6, pp. 9-16. 2006.
 19. Sugiyama, Kazunari, and Manabu Okumura. "Personal name disambiguation in web search results based on a semi-supervised clustering approach." In *Asian Digital Libraries. Looking Back 10 Years and Forging New Frontiers*, pp. 250-256. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2007.
 20. Lu, Zhao, Zhixian Yan, and Liang He. "OnPerDis: Ontology-Based Personal Name Disambiguation on the Web." In *Web Intelligence (WI) and Intelligent Agent Technologies (IAT)*, 2013 IEEE/WIC/ACM International Joint Conferences on, vol. 1, pp. 185-192. IEEE, 2013.
 21. Han, Xianpei, and Jun Zhao. "Web personal name disambiguation based on reference entity tables mined from the web." In *Proceedings of the eleventh international workshop on Web information and data management*, pp. 75-82. ACM, 2009.
 22. Guha and Garg. Disambiguating people in search. WWW'04.
 23. Mann, Gideon S., and David Yarowsky. "Unsupervised personal name disambiguation." In *Proceedings of the seventh conference on Natural language learning at HLT-NAACL 2003-Volume 4*, pp. 33-40. Association for Computational Linguistics, 2003.
 24. Jain, Anil K., M. Narasimha Murty, and Patrick J. Flynn. "Data clustering: a review." *ACM computing surveys (CSUR)* 31, no. 3 (1999): 264-323.
 25. <http://www.d.umn.edu/~tpederse/namedata.html>
 26. Manning, C.D., Raghavan, P., Schütze, H.: *Introduction to Information Retrieval*. Cambridge University Press (2008)
 27. Amigó, Enrique, Julio Gonzalo, Javier Artiles, and Felisa Verdejo. "A comparison of extrinsic clustering evaluation metrics based on formal constraints." *Information retrieval* 12, no. 4 (2009): 461-486.